

A novel concept of the management of coronary artery disease patients based on machine learning risk stratification and computational biomechanics: Preliminary results of SMARTool project

Antonios I. Sakellarios¹, Nikolaos Tachos¹, Elena Georga^{1,2}, George Rigas¹, Vassiliki Kigka^{1,2}, Panagiotis Siogkas^{1,2}, Georgia Karanasiou¹, Ioannis Andrikos^{1,2}, Panagiota Tsompou^{1,2}, Silvia Rocchiccioli³, Gualtriero Pelosi³, Oberdan Parodi³, Dimitrios I. Fotiadis^{1,2}

¹Department of Biomedical Research, Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology – FORTH, University Campus of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece

²Unit of Medical Technology and Intelligent Information Systems, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece

³Institute of Clinical Physiology, National Research Council, 56124, Pisa, Italy

Abstract. Coronary artery disease (CAD) is one of the most common causes of death in western societies. SMARTool project proposes a new concept for the risk stratification, diagnosis, prediction and treatment of CAD. Retrospective and prospective data (clinical, biohumoral, computed tomography coronary angiography (CTCA) imaging, omics, lipidomics, inflammatory and exposome) have been collected from ~250 patients. The proposed patient risk stratification, relying on machine learning analysis of non-imaging data, discriminates low and medium-to-high risk patients. The CAD diagnosis module is based on the 3D reconstruction and automatic blood flow dynamics of the coronary arteries, and the non-invasive estimation of smartFFR, an index correlated with invasively measured fractional flow reserve (FFR). CAD prediction is based on complex computational models of plaque growth considering the blood rheology, the lipoproteins transport and the major mechanisms of plaque growth, such as the inflammation and the foam cells formation. Finally, the treatment module is based on the simulation of virtual stent deployment. Preliminary analysis of 101 patients yielded an overall accuracy of 85.2% with the sensitivity of Class II reaching 98%. The reconstruction methodology is validated against intravascular ultrasound data and the correlation of the geometry derived metrics such as the degree of stenosis, minimal lumen area, minimal lumen diameter, plaque burden are 0.79, 0.85, 0.81 and 0.75, respectively. SmartFFR has been validated compared to invasively measured FFR with a correlation coefficient of 0.90. Plaque growth modelling demonstrates that the inclusion of variables such as the macrophages and foam cells concentrations can increase to 75% the prediction accuracy of regions prone to plaque formation.

Keywords: Coronary artery disease, risk stratification, Computational modeling.

1 Introduction

Despite the improvements in practices for the prevention of coronary artery disease (CAD), it is still considered as one of the leading causes of death in west societies [1]. Several factors contribute to CAD evolution including pathologic comorbid conditions such as hypertension, diabetes, hyperlipidemia, but also epigenetics and environmental influences such as the family history, gender and age. A major advance in CAD prevention is the use of computed tomography coronary angiography (CTCA) for visualizing and assessing the CAD severity. The continuously improvement of CTCA spatial resolution will further enhance its capability to prevent bad future events [2]. Besides the advances in imaging of CAD non-invasively, further achievements are made in understanding of the pathophysiology of plaque progression. In particular, several clinical trials attempt to collect patients' data under well-defined protocols aiming to search predictors and potential biomarkers, which are related to disease establishment and/or progression [3]. The main finding from large scale studies is that hemodynamics and especially low endothelial shear stress (ESS) affects the local phenotype of endothelial membrane promoting the atherosclerotic process [4]. Besides low ESS, other predictors of plaque progression are the increased plaque burden and lumen reduction at the baseline [5]. The recent years, computational modelling has been used further for simulating pathways and mechanisms of atherosclerosis initiating from the modelling of LDL transport and proving the association of LDL accumulation with disease progression [6]. Furthermore, complex models have been developed, which simulate the major steps of atherosclerosis such as the inflammation and the formation of smooth muscle cells [7].

Over the recent years, there has been major progress in systems medicine and multi-scale modelling approaches to human disease, boosted by the advent of high throughput omics technologies and the generation of genetic and molecular big data specific to an individual's personal profile. Although these offer huge potential for improving human health, reducing healthcare demand and promoting sustainable healthcare systems, they have only sporadically been used to explore well-being, disease prevention or rehabilitation. In this work we present a novel concept for the management of CAD patients non-invasively utilizing CTCA imaging. In particular, our concept is based on machine learning algorithm for the risk stratification of patients and continues with the computationally assessment of diagnosis, prognosis and treatment. This work is performed under the SMARTool project.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Concept of SMARTool

SMARTool project aims to deliver an idealized platform for the risk stratification, diagnosis, prognosis and treatment decision support for CAD patients. For this purpose retrospective patients' data are acquired from the EVINCI database [8] and prospective from the same patient population after a follow-up period of 5 ± 2 years. At

the moment baseline and follow-up data from 263 patients are collected. Each dataset includes CTCA imaging and clinical, molecular, biohumoral, inflammatory, omics and lipidomics information. Their collection in two time points offer the capability to estimate the disease progression. The first step of the proposed concept is to provide a risk stratification scoring system based on machine learning techniques in order to identify in parallel biomarkers and predictors of CAD existence or not. The second step is to build decision support systems (DSS) for the diagnosis, prognosis and treatment of CAD in realistic patient's scenarios (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. The proposed overall concept of SMARTool.

2.2 CAD risk stratification

A multiclass classification problem is defined based on an established risk score of coronary atherosclerosis combining markers of stenosis severity, plaque location and composition, as assessed by computed tomography angiography. A multimodal architecture approach is selected whose generalization capability, with respect to CAD stratification, is currently evaluated. First, the following feature classes (or views) were defined: (View 1) demographics, (View 2) clinical data, risk factors, symptoms, (View 3) molecular variables (i.e. biohumoral, inflammatory markers and lipids profile), (View 4) gene expression data, (View 5) exposome, and (View 6) monocytes. The multimodal architecture consists of two processing layers which are defined according to late or intermediate data integration strategies. Late data integration consists in the construction of: (i) an ensemble of decision tree-based prediction models (i.e. random forests, boosted decision trees) for each data view, whose individual decisions are effectively merged using simple mechanisms (e.g. weighted voting), or (ii) a multimodal deep neural network comprising appropriate deep learning subnetworks for each separate data view and, unifying their output into higher network layers. Intermediate data integration is based on multiple kernel learning. Kernel matri-

ces are computed for each data view, and then they are combined, through a parametric linear function, in order to generate the final kernel matrix. Kernel-based classification (i.e. support vector machine, relevance vector machine) is subsequently applied to predict CAD risk stratification. Finally, early integration schemes, which concatenate all features into a single vector, accompanied by appropriate feature selection algorithms were implemented for comparison purposes.

2.3 CAD diagnosis DSS

SmartFFR is our proposed new index for the assessment of the significance of coronary stenoses in coronary bifurcations. The aim of the current study is to compare SmartFFR with the Fractional Flow Reserve (FFR) values deriving from direct invasive pressure measurements from a dedicated pressure wire. In the context of the SMARTool study, 22 patients with chest pain symptoms and intermediate pre-test likelihood of CAD underwent CCTA as well as FFR measurement. The 24 left arterial branches which included the LAD and the LCx were reconstructed using our in-house developed software. We performed two computational blood flow simulations for each case to calculate the SmartFFR for each 3D model. Regarding the inlet, the average patient-specific pressure at rest was applied as a boundary condition. Assuming a myocardial blood flow of 2 ml/s and 6 ml/s during rest and under stress for the Left Main artery, respectively, we calculated the flow for each branch using Murray's law and applied it as outlet boundary conditions. SmartFFR was calculated for each branch by computing the ratio of distal to proximal pressure for a range of flows between 0 and 4 ml/s, normalized by the respective ratio of a normal artery.

2.4 CAD prognosis DSS

The prognosis DSS of SMARTool is based on the prediction of site-specific plaque growth. This is achieved by implementing a multi-level modelling approach. The first level of our approach is the utilization of CTCA images for the 3D reconstruction of coronary arteries. The methodology was previously presented in [9]. In the second level, blood flow modelling is employed by using the Navier-Stokes equations. In the third level mass transport modelling is performed considering as mass the LDL, the high density lipoproteins (HDL) and the monocytes. The mass is transported in the lumen and in the arterial wall by employing the convection-diffusion equations. Additionally, we assume that the endothelial membrane is semi-permeable and the Kedem-Katchalsky equations are used to estimate the molecular penetration [10]. The fourth level of prognosis DSS is the modelling of plaque growth and more specifically, the modelling of the atherosclerotic pathways of disease evolution. These pathways are representing the oxidation of LDL molecules, considering however the atheroprotective effect of HDL. The transformation of monocytes to macrophages is also modelled applying a diffusion equation, while in parallel the endocytosis of oxidized LDL by macrophages is modelled. Finally, the formation of foam cells and plaque is modelled after considering the density of each molecule in combination with their concentration.

2.5 CAD treatment DSS

The treatment DSS of SMARTool is based on the modelling of stent deployment in stenosed coronary arteries. More specifically, the finite element model consists of the reconstructed artery and the stent, in their unexpanded configurations. The stent is inflated through a pressure driven approach as following: (i) loading (P=0 to 1.8MPa), (ii) holding (P=1.8MPa constant) and, (iii) unloading (P=1.8 to 0MPa). Appropriate boundary conditions are imposed in the ends of the artery and the stent. A frictionless contact is assumed for the inner arterial wall-stent contact pair. The results show that the stent design characteristics and the material influence the resulting stress field imposed on the arterial wall. From the analysis of the models the following parameters are examined: (i) Von Mises stress in the arterial wall. (ii) Von Mises stress in the stent scaffold. (iii) Stent directional deformation.

3 Results

For the risk stratification tool the following cases are tested: i) Case 1: Demographics, Risk Factors, ii) Case 2: Demographics, Risk Factors, Symptoms, iii) Case 3: Demographics, Risk Factors, Symptoms, Molecular Systemic Variables, iv) Case 4: Feature ranking according to the InfoGain criterion. Also the following machine learning algorithms are implemented: i) Feed-forward neural network; ii) Support vector machine; iii) Random forest. The Table 1 shows that for the current dataset of 101 patients the SVM algorithm outperforms the other especially for the Case 4. The main outcome, however, is that the inclusion of more kinds of data moving from Case 1 to Case 4 increases the accuracy results of all classification algorithms.

Table 1. Accuracy, sensitivity and specificity for the various algorithms for the four cases.

	MLP			SVM			RF		
	Acc.	Se.	Sp.	Acc.	Se.	Sp.	Acc.	Se.	Sp.
Case 1	66.3	78.9	28.0	77.2	97.4	16.0	73.3	85.5	36.0
Case 2	70.3	81.6	36.0	81.2	94.7	40.0	75.2	88.2	36.0
Case 3	74.3	84.2	44.0	84.2	97.4	44.0	77.2	97.4	16.0
Case 4	78.2	90.8	40.0	85.1	98.7	44.0	81.2	92.1	48.0

The 3D reconstruction methodology is validated using IVUS-VH images. The correlation coefficients of the IVUS based reconstruction with the proposed methodology for the degree of stenosis, the plaque burden, the minimal lumen area and the minimal lumen diameter, were 0.79, 0.75, 0.85, 0.81, respectively. The reconstructed arteries are used for the modelling of blood flow, mass transport and plaque growth. The preliminary analysis of about 60 patients demonstrate that a multivariate model which include all computational variables such as the macrophages and foam cells concentrations increase the prediction accuracy of regions prone to plaque formation to 75%. Figure 2 shows a case example, where baseline calculations predict the *de-novo* plaque at the follow-up (right panel).

We implement a novel approach named SmartFFR in order to assess the hemodynamic status of coronary bifurcations. In the context of the SMARTool study, 24 patients with chest pain symptoms and intermediate pre-test likelihood of CAD underwent CCTA as well as FFR measurement. The 24 left arterial branches (29 arteries) which included the LAD and the LCx were reconstructed using our in-house developed software. Strong correlation ($r=0.87$, $P<0.0001$) was found between the two methods, while all pathological cases presenting ischemia, were correctly categorized by our method as hemodynamically significant lesions.

Fig. 2. A patient example where the simulated results of shear stress and high LDL concentration are related to a new formed plaque at the follow-up.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

SMARTool aims to the development of a cloud-based platform which is based on a novel concept for the management of atherosclerosis. The excellence of SMARTool arises from the unique attempt to address the most recent guidelines and directions proposed by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) [11]. ESC argues that CAD risk must be assessed in younger ages (<50 years old). American Heart Association proposes to consider also the genetic profile for prevention of CAD. Moreover, ESC proposes that risk factor intervention must be at the individual level and ideally non-invasively. SMARTool attempts to identify novel biomarkers of disease progression and integrate them in models and tools for the early diagnosis and prevention of CAD. The preliminary results show that SMARTool can provide a comprehensive platform for the risk stratification as well as DSS for the diagnosis, prognosis and treatment of CAD. In particular, it provides a novel risk stratification scheme taking under consideration the molecular and genetic patient's profile. Additionally, it delivers validated algorithms and tools for the 3D reconstruction of arteries using CTCA, which allows the non-invasive estimation of SmartFFR index (highly correlated to FFR for diagnosis), but also the site-specific prediction of plaque growth.

References

- [1] W. H. O. (WHO). *The atlas of heart disease and stroke*. Available: http://www.who.int/cardiovascular_diseases/en/cvd_atlas_16_death_from_stroke.pdf
- [2] S. L. Papadopoulou *et al.*, "Natural History of Coronary Atherosclerosis by Multislice Computed Tomography," (in English), *Jacc-Cardiovascular Imaging*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. S28-S37, Mar 2012.
- [3] P. H. Stone *et al.*, "Role of Low Endothelial Shear Stress and Plaque Characteristics in the Prediction of Nonculprit Major Adverse Cardiac Events: The PROSPECT Study," *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging*, Sep 18 2017.
- [4] Y. S. Chatzizisis, A. U. Coskun, M. Jonas, E. R. Edelman, C. L. Feldman, and P. H. Stone, "Role of endothelial shear stress in the natural history of coronary atherosclerosis and vascular remodeling - Molecular, cellular, and vascular behavior," (in English), *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, vol. 49, no. 25, pp. 2379-2393, Jun 26 2007.
- [5] C. V. Bourantas *et al.*, "Noninvasive Prediction of Atherosclerotic Progression: The PROSPECT-MSCT Study," *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1009-11, Aug 2016.
- [6] A. Sakellarios *et al.*, "Prediction of atherosclerotic disease progression using LDL transport modelling: a serial computed tomographic coronary angiographic study," *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Imaging*, Mar 16 2016.
- [7] A. Sakellarios *et al.*, "Prediction of Atherosclerotic Plaque Development in an in Vivo Coronary Arterial Segment Based on a Multi-level Modeling Approach," *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng*, Oct 19 2016.
- [8] R. Liga *et al.*, "Multicentre multi-device hybrid imaging study of coronary artery disease: results from the EVAluation of INtegrated Cardiac Imaging for the Detection and Characterization of Ischaemic Heart Disease (EVINCI) hybrid imaging population," *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Imaging*, vol. 17, no. 9, pp. 951-60, Sep 2016.
- [9] A. I. Sakellarios *et al.*, "SMARTool: A tool for clinical decision support for the management of patients with coronary artery disease based on modeling of atherosclerotic plaque process," *Conf Proc IEEE Eng Med Biol Soc*, vol. 2017, pp. 96-99, Jul 2017.
- [10] A. I. Sakellarios *et al.*, "Patient-specific computational modeling of subendothelial LDL accumulation in a stenosed right coronary artery: effect of hemodynamic and biological factors," (in English), *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology*, vol. 304, no. 11, pp. H1455-H1470, Jun 2013.
- [11] M. F. Piepoli *et al.*, "2016 European Guidelines on cardiovascular disease prevention in clinical practice: The Sixth Joint Task Force of the European Society of Cardiology and Other Societies on Cardiovascular Disease Prevention in Clinical Practice (constituted by representatives of 10 societies and by invited experts)Developed with the special contribution of the European Association for Cardiovascular Prevention & Rehabilitation (EACPR)," *Eur Heart J*, vol. 37, no. 29, pp. 2315-81, Aug 1 2016.